

Antioxidant potential and nutritional content of stem, bark and pod of Drumstick tree (*Moringa oleifera* Lam.) from semi-arid region of Haryana

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Abstract : Different parts of *Moringa oleifera* (stem, pod and bark) were extracted with hot methanol and different fractions were made using solvents of different polarity. These extracts were used to evaluate total phenolics content, total flavonoids content, total alkaloid content, mineral content and free radical scavenging activity by DPPH method. Total phenolics content was highest in acetone fraction of pod (41.27 ± 0.10 mg GAE/g) while total flavonoids content was highest in ethyl acetate fraction of stem (71.00 ± 0.33 mg CE/g). The amount of total alkaloids varied from 12.50 ± 0.50 mg BNE/g (acetone fraction of bark) to 181.83 ± 0.76 mg BNE/g (methanol fraction of pod). *Moringa oleifera* possess the highest K content (14905.00 ± 1.23 mg/100 g) in water fraction of pod, followed by N (1275.00 ± 0.56 mg/100 g) in acetone fraction of stem, Zn (556.70 ± 0.14 mg/100 g) in acetone fraction of stem, P (531.25 ± 0.34 mg/100 g) in water fraction of pod, Fe (24.63 ± 0.67 mg/100 g) in acetone fraction of bark, Cu (7.11 ± 0.01 mg/100 g) in ethyl acetate fraction of pod and Mn (3.84 ± 0.02 mg/100 g) in acetone fraction of bark. Acetone fraction of *Moringa* pod exhibited highest antioxidant activity having IC₅₀ value 263.18 µg/ml.

Keywords : *Moringa oleifera*, total phenolics, flavonoids, antioxidant activity, mineral content, total alkaloid.

Introduction

Reactive oxygen species (ROS) such as O₂⁻, H₂O₂ and OH⁻ are produced in human body as a consequence of a number of metabolic processes involving redox enzymes and bioenergetic electron transfer reactions¹. These reactive oxygen species induce oxidative damage to various biomolecules including proteins, lipids, lipoproteins and DNA² which lead to several human diseases such as cancer, diabetes, arthritis, neurodegenerative diseases and ageing processes^{3,4}. So, these ROS need to be scavenged either by body's internal antioxidant systems or by external antioxidants. Many synthetic antioxidants like BHA (Butylated Hydroxy Anisole) are available commercially but these are not safe⁵. Natural antioxidants and plant derived natural extracts are safe and bioactive.

Moringa oleifera, which belongs to Moringaceae family, is the most widely cultivated pan-tropical species. It is native to the sub-Himalayan tracts of India, Pakistan, Bangladesh and Afghanistan⁶. It is commonly known as

horseradish tree, drumstick tree (English), munga (Hindi) and sajina (Bengali). It is a small, fast growing, ever-green, or deciduous tree that usually grows upto 10 or 12 m in height⁷. It has a spreading, open crown of drooping, fragile branches, feathery foliage of tripinnate leaves and thick corky, whitish bark⁸. The tree produces a tuberous tap root which explains its tolerance to drought conditions.

Almost every part of *Moringa oleifera* is edible and widely used in traditional medicine because of the presence of several phytochemicals like tannins, alkaloids, phenolic compounds, amino acids, sterols and carbohydrates⁷. Its flowers and roots are used in folk remedies for tumors and the seeds for abdominal tumors. Barks are boiled in water and soaked in alcohol to obtain drinks and infusions that can be used to treat stomach ailments, poor vision, joint pain, diabetes, anemia and hypertension⁹.

Moringa oleifera exhibited antiinflammatory, antihypertensive, diuretic, antimicrobial, antioxidant, antidia-

betic, antihyperlipidemic, antineoplastic, antipyretic, antiulcer, cardioprotectant, and hepatoprotectant activities¹⁰. Various reports^{11,12} are available which describe the antioxidant potential of various parts of *Moringa oleifera* but screening of different solvent fractions of *Moringa oleifera* from semi-arid zone of Haryana has not been carried out. Therefore, the present study was aimed to screen the various solvent fractions of stem, bark and pod of *Moringa oleifera* for total phenolics content (TPC), total flavonoids content (TFC), total alkaloid content, mineral content and their free radical scavenging activity.

Results and discussion

Total phenolics content :

Plant phenolics are secondary metabolites which are aromatic in nature and are high level antioxidants because of their ability to scavenge free radicals and active oxygen species. It is well known that phenolic substances contribute directly to the antioxidant activity of plant materials. In fact, phenolic compounds exhibit considerable free radical-scavenging activities (through their reactivity as hydrogen-donating or electron-donating agents) and metal ion-chelating properties. Therefore, the amount of total phenolics in different solvent fractions of drumstick tree pod, stem and bark were determined (Fig. 1).

The TPCs of various fractions of *Moringa oleifera* is expressed in terms of gallic acid equivalent (GAE) and is calculated using the following linear regression equation

Fig. 1. Total phenolics content (mg GAE/g) of pod, bark and stem of *Moringa oleifera*.

obtained from standard plot of gallic acid.

$$y = 0.0167x - 0.0095, R^2 = 0.999$$

where y is the absorbance and x is the amount of gallic acid in μg .

Our results showed that the content of total phenolics varied from 2.02 ± 0.04 mg GAE/g of extract (hexane fraction of bark) to 41.27 ± 0.10 mg GAE/g of extract (acetone fraction of pod). Acetone fraction of stem, bark and pod of *Moringa oleifera* was found to contain the highest amount of total phenols.

Total flavonoids content :

Flavonoids are probably the most important class of natural phenolics and have the ability to donate electrons or hydrogen atoms readily, so they can directly scavenge reactive oxygen species. They are also known to act as antioxidant, both as radical scavengers and as metal chelators. So, the total flavonoid content of various fractions of *Moringa oleifera* was determined. The TFCs are expressed in terms of catechin equivalent (CE) and are presented in Fig. 2. The TFCs were calculated using the following linear regression equation obtained from the standard plot of catechin :

$$y = 0.0038x + 0.0019, R^2 = 0.9968$$

where y is the absorbance and x is the amount of catechin in μg .

The amount of total flavonoids in all fractions of stem,

Fig. 2. Total flavonoids content (mg CE/g) of pod, bark and stem of *Moringa oleifera*.

bark and pod of *Moringa oleifera* varied from 0.22 ± 0.19 mg CE/g (hexane fraction of bark) to 71.00 ± 0.33 mg CE/g (ethyl acetate fraction of stem). Among all solvent fractions, ethyl acetate fraction was found to contain the highest amount of total flavonoids.

Total alkaloids content :

The determination of alkaloids is important as they are responsible for various therapeutic properties of plants. The medicinal properties of plants are not due to the presence of a single component but it is attributed to the synergistic action of various chemical components present in the plant. Keeping this in mind, the alkaloid content of various fractions of stem, bark and pod of *Moringa oleifera* was determined. The TAC is expressed in terms of bismuth nitrate equivalent (BNE) in Fig. 3. The amount of total alkaloid content was calculated using the following linear regression equation obtained from the standard plot of bismuth nitrate.

$$y = 0.0023x - 0.0136, R^2 = 0.9964$$

where *y* is the absorbance and *x* is the amount of bismuth

Fig. 3. Total alkaloids content (mg BNE/g) of pod, bark and stem of *Moringa oleifera*.

nitrate in μg .

The TAC of various fractions of stem, bark and pod of *Moringa oleifera* varied from 12.50 ± 0.50 mg BNE/g (acetone fraction of bark) to 181.83 ± 0.76 mg BNE/g (methanol fraction of pod). Among various fractions of pod, methanol fraction was found to contain the highest amount of total alkaloids while in stem and bark, ethyl acetate fraction has the highest amount of total alkaloids.

Mineral content :

Moringa oleifera is one of the most important medicinal plant with many healing benefits and high nutrient composition. Therefore, the mineral composition of stem, bark and pod of this plant was estimated. The results of our study revealed that *Moringa oleifera* possess the highest potassium (K) content, followed by nitrogen (N), zinc (Zn), phosphorus (P), iron (Fe), copper (Cu) and manganese (Mn) content (Tables 1, 2 and 3). K content was minimum in ethyl acetate fraction of bark sample (17.50 ± 0.87 mg/100 g) and maximum in water fraction of pod sample (14905.00 ± 1.23 mg/100 g). K plays an important role in regulation of acid-base concentration and water in blood and tissues. It prevents stroke by maintaining proper functioning of brain and nerves¹³. Fe content ranges from 0.63 ± 0.03 mg/100 g (ethyl acetate fraction of bark) to 24.63 ± 0.67 mg/100 g (acetone fraction of bark). Iron plays an important role in the formation of oxygen transport proteins namely, haemoglobin and myoglobin¹⁴.

Moringa oleifera is known as “Mother’s best friend” as it increases milk production in nursing mothers. This effect can be attributed to Cu and Zn content, which are

Table 1. Mineral content (mg/100 g) in various fractions of pod of *Moringa oleifera*

Fractions	Iron (Fe)	Copper (Cu)	Zinc (Zn)	Manganese (Mn)	Nitrogen (N)	Phosphorus (P)	Potassium (K)
Hexane	5.77 ± 0.34	ND	42.50 ± 0.45	0.05 ± 0.02	662.50 ± 0.67	225.00 ± 1.55	46.30 ± 2.58
Benzene	18.37 ± 1.02	0.37 ± 0.02	35.80 ± 2.58	0.19 ± 0.03	750.00 ± 0.87	112.50 ± 0.02	35.50 ± 0.01
Chloroform	4.88 ± 0.58	ND	31.70 ± 0.04	0.28 ± 0.03	850.00 ± 1.23	318.75 ± 0.34	1575.00 ± 1.23
Ethyl acetate	5.30 ± 0.67	7.11 ± 0.01	112.10 ± 0.34	0.33 ± 0.04	900.00 ± 1.45	225.00 ± 0.67	62.20 ± 0.04
Acetone	4.70 ± 0.88	2.25 ± 0.03	528.30 ± 1.23	2.66 ± 0.23	750.00 ± 0.45	368.75 ± 2.58	1910.00 ± 0.02
Water	10.91 ± 0.56	1.17 ± 0.02	308.70 ± 0.87	0.47 ± 0.01	662.50 ± 0.04	531.25 ± 0.34	14905.00 ± 1.23
Methanol	11.39 ± 0.33	1.09 ± 0.01	210.40 ± 0.04	0.44 ± 0.02	950.00 ± 0.08	368.75 ± 0.56	8555.00 ± 1.45

All the values are mean \pm S.D. (n = 3). ND – Not determined.

Table 2. Mineral content (mg/100 g) in various fractions of bark of *Moringa oleifera*

Fractions	Iron (Fe)	Copper (Cu)	Zinc (Zn)	Manganese (Mn)	Nitrogen (N)	Phosphorus (P)	Potassium (K)
Hexane	5.17±0.02	0.11±0.01	34.20±0.02	0.03±0.01	900.00±0.34	206.25±1.23	35.50±0.45
Benzene	4.18±1.23	0.84±0.03	57.20±0.01	0.15±0.01	800.00±1.23	81.25±1.55	40.90±0.04
Chloroform	13.88±0.04	1.78±0.05	101.50±0.88	ND	700.00±0.02	125.00±1.45	95.40±0.03
Ethyl acetate	0.63±0.03	2.31±0.03	108.40±0.15	0.32±0.04	612.50±0.08	262.50±0.01	17.50±0.87
Acetone	24.63±0.67	1.51±0.02	544.80±1.55	3.84±0.02	900.00±0.15	181.25±0.67	1346.50±0.15
Water	21.43±1.45	1.20±0.15	399.30±0.33	0.40±0.01	800.00±1.02	468.75±2.58	1385.00±1.55
Methanol	13.09±0.02	0.35±0.04	162.70±0.56	ND	1000.00±0.58	262.50±0.34	8205.00±0.03

All the values are mean±S.D. (n = 3). ND – Not determined.

Table 3. Mineral content (mg/100 g) in various fractions of stem of *Moringa oleifera*

Fractions	Iron (Fe)	Copper (Cu)	Zinc (Zn)	Manganese (Mn)	Nitrogen (N)	Phosphorus (P)	Potassium (K)
Hexane	13.76±0.01	0.47±0.14	57.90±1.55	0.20±0.01	750.00±0.03	468.70±1.45	185.30±0.33
Benzene	13.92±2.58	2.60±0.02	79.50±0.15	0.28±0.04	800.00±0.87	318.75±2.58	117.30±1.55
Chloroform	10.77±0.34	3.56±0.45	74.00±0.14	0.21±0.02	662.50±0.02	293.75±0.01	30.30±0.88
Ethyl acetate	3.23±1.55	1.37±0.15	83.20±0.01	0.28±0.03	750.00±0.67	262.50±0.33	27.70±0.56
Acetone	9.46±0.87	1.78±0.05	556.70±0.14	0.24±0.03	1275.00±0.56	81.25±0.58	269.30±0.01
Water	8.16±0.14	2.30±0.67	121.80±0.03	0.27±0.01	800.00±3.18	318.75±0.02	13065.00±0.05
Methanol	6.39±0.08	0.21±0.03	145.10±0.04	0.24±0.02	900.00±0.05	356.25±1.55	6025.00±0.67

All the volumes are mean±S.D. (n = 3).

essential for increasing the rate of milk production in pregnant females¹⁵. Hence, Cu and Zn content were evaluated. Cu content was found to be minimum in hexane fraction of bark (0.11±0.01 mg/100 g) and maximum in ethyl acetate fraction of pod (7.11±0.01 mg/100 g) whereas Zn content varied from 31.70±0.04 mg/100 g in chloroform fraction of pod to 556.70±0.14 mg/100 g in acetone fraction of stem. Zn enhances the function of immune system and proper functioning of enzymes such as those involved in cell division and growth¹⁶. However, the level of Mn content was quite low as compared to other minerals i.e. from 0.03±0.01 mg/100 g (hexane fraction of bark) to 3.84±0.02 mg/100 g (acetone fraction of bark). Mn helps in breaking down of fats, carbohydrates and proteins. Among all fractions, water fraction of pod (531.25±0.34 mg/100 g) was found to contain the highest amount of P and benzene fraction of bark (81.25±1.55 mg/100 g) and acetone fraction of stem (81.25±0.58 mg/100 g) contain the lowest amount of P. The concentration of N ranges from 612.50±0.08 mg/100 g (ethyl acetate fraction of bark) to 1275.00±0.56 mg/100 g (acetone fraction of stem). The results of mineral analysis demonstrated a significant variation in the mineral content in different

solvent fractions of *Moringa oleifera*.

DPPH free radical scavenging activity :

2,2'-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl radical is one of the few stable and commercially available organic nitrogen radical (DPPH[•]), often used in evaluation of radical scavenging activity of antioxidants – natural and synthetic pure compounds¹⁷, plant extracts¹⁸ and foods¹⁹. Alcoholic solutions of DPPH[•] have a characteristic absorption maximum at 517 nm. When an electron or hydrogen atom donating antioxidant (AH) is added to DPPH[•], a decrease in absorbance at 517 nm takes place due to the formation of the non-radical form DPPH-H which does not absorb at 517 nm. This reaction is measured by de-coloration assay where the decrease in absorbance at 517 nm produced by the addition of the antioxidant to the DPPH[•] in methanol or ethanol is measured.

All the fractions of stem, bark and pod were screened for free radical scavenging activity against DPPH. The most active type of fraction was acetone in all the three plant parts. This might be due to the presence of lower phenols and non-glycosylated flavonols which are generally more

soluble in acetone. Among acetone fractions, pod's acetone fraction has the lowest value of IC_{50} i.e. 263.18 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ followed by bark (323.89 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) and stem (484.65 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) (Fig. 4). This suggests that the acetone fraction of pod of *Moringa oleifera* may contain higher concentrations of active compounds needed in reaction of DPPH scavenging. These results also correlate with total pheno-

Fig. 4. IC_{50} ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) values for various fractions of *Moringa oleifera*.

lics content which is also higher in acetone fraction. Generally, higher polyphenolic content corresponds with higher antioxidant activity which might be due to the combined action of present substances in variable concentrations and their hydrogen atom donating abilities. However, the higher polarity solvent fractions were not the most active as the radical scavenging activity of a particular antioxidant depends on structure as well as on the type of reaction kinetics²⁰.

Experimental

Chemicals :

Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, thiourea, catechin and 1,1-diphenyl-2-picryl hydrazyl (DPPH) were obtained from Himedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., Nashik, Mumbai. Gallic acid, aluminium chloride, bismuth nitrate, disodium sulphide, butylated hydroxy anisole (BHA), sodium hydroxide, sodium silicate, Neseller's reagent, 2,4-dinitrophenol (DNP), ammonium molybdate, ammonium vandate and

potassium iodide were purchased from CDH, Daryaganj, New Delhi. All other chemicals and solvents used in the study were of analytical grade and purchased from CDH or SD Fine Chem Limited, Mumbai.

Collection of plant material :

Different parts of *Moringa oleifera* namely, stem, pod and bark were procured in the month of May from campus of CCS HAU, Hisar, Haryana, India. All the collected plant samples were washed thoroughly with water and shadow-dried. These samples were then chopped into small pieces and kept in air tight containers for further use.

Preparation of extracts/fractions :

All the plant samples of *Moringa oleifera* viz. stem, bark and pod were extracted with hot methanol by refluxing method for 8 h. The process was repeated thrice and the respective extractives were pooled together. The obtained extractives were evaporated on a rotary evaporator to give a crude extract which was further fractionated in different solvents viz. hexane, benzene, chloroform, ethyl acetate, acetone and water. Each obtained fraction was evaporated to give a crude mass and stored in a refrigerator till use.

Estimation of total phenolics content (TPC) :

The TPC of various fractions of *Moringa oleifera* was determined by using Folin-Ciocalteu method²¹. Gallic acid (2.5–50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was used as a reference standard for plotting calibration curve. 1 ml of each plant fraction (1 mg/ml) was mixed with 1 ml of 1 N Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and then added 1 ml saturated solution of 20% sodium carbonate. The final volume was made upto 10 ml using distilled water. The reaction mixture was kept in dark for colour development at room temperature for 20 min. The absorbance was measured at a wavelength of 725 nm using UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The amount of total phenolics was determined using linear regression equation obtained from the standard curve of gallic acid. The total phenolics content was calculated as mean \pm Standard Deviation (S.D.) and expressed as mg/g

gallic acid equivalent (GAE) of extract.

Estimation of total flavonoid content (TFC) :

The TFC was determined by aluminium chloride colorimetric assay²² and catechin was used as a reference standard to construct a calibration curve. Briefly, 10 mg of catechin was dissolved in 100 ml of distilled water and then diluted to give various concentrations of 2.5, 5, 10, 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 µg/ml. 1 ml of each fraction and standard catechin were mixed separately with 4 ml of distilled water, 0.3 ml of 5% sodium nitrite and 0.3 ml of 10% aluminium chloride in a 10 ml volumetric flask. After 5 min, added 2 ml of 1 M sodium hydroxide solution and the final volume was made upto the mark with distilled water. The absorbance of the reaction mixture was measured at 510 nm on UV-Visible spectrophotometer against a blank containing all reagents except plant sample. The amount of flavonoid was calculated from linear regression equation obtained from calibration curve of catechin. The TFC was calculated as mean ± S.D. and expressed as mg/g catechin equivalent (CE) of extract.

Estimation of total alkaloid content (TAC) :

The total alkaloid content was determined by spectrophotometric method of Dragendorff's reagent²³. 5 ml of each plant fraction was mixed with 1 ml of 0.1 N HCl and the pH was maintained at 2–2.5 with dilute HCl. Then 2.5 ml of Dragendorff's reagent was added to it and the precipitate formed was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 5 min. After centrifugation, the centrifugate was decanted completely and the precipitate was further washed with 2.5 ml of ethanol. The filtrate was discarded and the residue was then treated with 2.5 ml of disodium sulfide. The brownish black precipitate formed was then centrifuged again at 3000 rpm for 5 min. The completion of precipitation was checked by adding two drops of disodium sulfide. The residue was dissolved in 2 ml of concentrated nitric acid, with warming, if necessary. This solution was diluted to 10 ml in a standard volumetric flask with distilled water. 1 ml of this solution was taken and mixed with 5 ml of thiourea solution. The absorbance of this solution was measured at 435 nm against a blank containing 1 ml of nitric acid and 5 ml of thiourea. The standard

curve was prepared using 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, and 100 µg/ml of bismuth nitrate solution. The amount of total alkaloid was calculated as mean ± S.D. from linear regression equation obtained from calibration plot of bismuth nitrate and expressed as mg/g bismuth nitrate equivalent (BNE) of extract.

Estimation of mineral content :

Minerals (Fe, Cu, Zn and Mn) were determined by using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer. The samples were digested by wet oxidation. 0.5 g of each fraction was taken and 20 ml of diacid mixture (HNO₃ : HClO₄ – 4 : 1) was added to each and kept overnight. Next day, the samples were digested on hot plate and the final volume was made upto 25 ml using distilled water. The readings were taken on AAS against a blank. The mineral content was determined by using the following formula and expressed as mg/100 g of the extract.

Mineral content =

$$(\text{Abs}_{\text{Sample}} - \text{Abs}_{\text{Blank}}) \times \text{Dilution factor}$$

For nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium, the plant fractions were digested by following the same procedure but instead of HNO₃ : HClO₄ – 4 : 1, 10 ml of H₂SO₄ : HClO₄ – 4 : 1 diacid mixture is used. Nitrogen content was determined by colorimetric (Nessler's reagent) method²⁴. 0.2 ml of each plant digest was taken in 25 ml volumetric flask and added 0.5 ml of 10% sodium hydroxide and 1 ml of 10% sodium silicate solution to it. For color development, 1 ml of Nessler's reagent was added to each flask and the final volume was made upto the mark. The absorbance of the samples was read at 440 nm using spectronic²⁰ UV-Visible spectrophotometer against a blank. The concentration of nitrogen was determined by using standard curve of ammonium sulphate and expressed in mg/100 g.

Phosphorus content was also determined by Vanadomolybdo – phosphoric yellow color method²⁵. 2 ml of plant digest was taken in a volumetric flask and added 1–2 drops of 2,4-dinitrophenol and then added ammonia solution till the development of yellow color. After color development added HCl dropwise till it became colorless and then added 5 ml of ammonium molybdate-

vandate solution to each flask. Now make the final volume upto the mark and read the absorbance at 440 nm using blue filter on Spectronic 20 spectrophotometer against a reagent blank. The phosphorus content (mg/100 g) was determined by using the standard plot of potassium chloride. Potassium content in acid digest of plant samples was determined by taking reading on Flame Photometer against a reagent blank. The concentration of potassium (mg/100 g) was determined by using the standard curve of potassium chloride.

DPPH free radical scavenging activity :

The antioxidant activity of different fractions of *Moringa oleifera* and standard butylated hydroxy anisole (BHA) was evaluated by using DPPH (2,2'-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) method²⁶. 1 ml of each fraction and standard at different test concentrations was added to 2.5 ml of 0.1 mM DPPH solution taken in test tubes. The solution was mixed rapidly and allowed to stand in dark at 37 °C for 30 min. The decrease in absorbance was measured at 517 nm using UV-Visible spectrophotometer against a blank prepared similarly without sample. The percentage antioxidant activity was calculated by using the equation :

$$\%DPPH^*_{sc} = \{(A_{cont} - A_{samp})/A_{cont}\} \times 100$$

where A_{cont} is the absorbance of control and A_{samp} is the absorbance of sample.

The concentration of sample required to scavenge 50% of DPPH radical (IC_{50}) was also determined by using regression equation obtained by plotting the curve of percent inhibition with their respective concentrations.

Data analysis :

All the experimental measurements were carried out in triplicate and results were presented as mean \pm standard deviation. Statistical analysis was carried out using Microsoft Excel 2007.

Conclusion

In this study it was concluded that *Moringa oleifera* contain good amount of total phenols and flavonoids. It also acts as a rich source of all the minerals. Among different fractions, acetone fraction of pod was found to offer the most efficient antioxidant activity which reveals

its potency as a good source of natural antioxidant. However, further research is needed to identify individual components forming antioxidative systems and develop their application for food and pharmaceutical industries.

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